

GAME METHODS AS A MEANS OF EFFECTIVE INFLUENCE ON COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8022394>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 01-June 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 05-June 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 10-June 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

gaming method, purpose and objectives of the gaming method, classification of games.

ABSTRACT

The use of gaming teaching methods in the classroom allows you to effectively influence the cognitive activity of younger students, as well as increase motivation for learning. The article considers the classification of gaming teaching methods and provides examples of games that can be played in the classroom.

INTRODUCTION

Game methods have an advantage over other teaching methods, as they are interesting for children and attract attention from the very beginning. Gaming methods are based on various games that evoke positive emotions that help create a comfortable psychological situation in the learning process. The use of gaming methods in teaching significantly reduces the cost of nervous energy and volitional efforts. In the process of studying the use of gaming teaching methods, it was found that these methods contribute to the strengthening of the mental and motor activity of students. Motor activity has a positive effect on the formation of associative links that cover the process of mastering knowledge and skills. During the game, the child's perception processes proceed much faster and more accurately.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Analysis and synthesis of psychological, pedagogical and methodical literature, normative documents; monitoring the course of the pedagogical process; questioning; conducting experiential learning.

DISCUSSION

Game teaching methods are methods that, in a game form, recreate situations aimed at mastering the norms and rules of behavior in society, contribute to the formation of social experience, and improve the skills of self-management of behavior. Everyone is well aware that the beginning of a child's education at school is a difficult and responsible stage in his life. Children of six or seven years old are experiencing a psychological crisis associated with the need to adapt at school. The child undergoes a change in the leading activity: before going to school, children are mainly engaged in playing, and when they come to school, they begin to master learning activities. The transition from play to learning activity is usually imposed on the child by adults, and does not occur

naturally. How to help a child? Games that will create optimal psychological conditions for the successful development of the personality of a younger student will undoubtedly become a great helper in this. The concept of "game" includes a huge range of ideas, and different authors approach the interpretation of this definition in their own way.

The Soviet teacher V.A. Sukhomlinsky wrote: "Without play, there can be no full-fledged mental development. The game is a huge bright window through which a life-giving stream of ideas and concepts flows into the spiritual world of the child. The game is a spark that ignites the flame of inquisitiveness and curiosity. In games, the attention of children, creative imagination is activated, computational skills, moral qualities of the individual are formed, a sense of responsibility, collectivism, discipline, will, character develop.

L. S. Vygotsky and his students consider the initial, determining in the game that a person, when playing, creates an imaginary situation for himself instead of a real one and acts in it, performing a certain role, in accordance with the transferable meanings that he attaches to surrounding objects.

The didactic task is determined by the purpose of teaching and educational influence. Game task defines game actions. Game actions are connected with the game plan. The more diverse they are, the more interesting the game, the more successfully cognitive and game tasks are solved. The rules of the game contain moral requirements and influence the solution of the didactic task. The result helps to identify children who performed the game task better. The teacher should note the achievements of each child, emphasize the successes of lagging behind children.

A.V. Konyshcheva identifies the following functions of gaming activity:

- 1) entertaining (arouse interest);
- 2) communicative (mastering the dialectics of communication);
- 3) diagnostic (identification of deviations from normative behavior, self-knowledge during the game);
- 4) game therapy (overcoming various difficulties arising in other types of life activities);
- 5) Self-realization (manifestation of abilities and hidden opportunities);
- 6) interethnic communication (assimilation of sociocultural values common to all people);
- 7) socialization (inclusion in the system of social relations);
- 8) aesthetic (pleasure that is experienced from the game)

During the lesson, several games can be played, connected by a single plot to each other. But a lesson consisting of one big game can also be held. According to such a game, the student gets a permanent role. Also, a certain game goal should be set before him, the conditions and rules of the game should be explained. Speaking about the actions of students during such a game, it should be noted that they depend on the hidden learning goal. For example, if the goal of the game is to develop a certain skill, then the students are given and explained the corresponding speech pattern, which they work out during the game. If the goal of the game is to develop the ability to speak, then a speech sample is usually not given, but visual supports are given (for example, pictures, photographs).

There are six main purposes of using the game in the classroom:

- 1) development of the necessary abilities and mental functions;

- 2) development of certain speech skills;
- 3) formation of certain skills;
- 4) development of communication skills;
- 5) knowledge of the facts of culture;
- 6) involuntary memorization of speech material.

Consider the game in terms of target orientation. It is divided into:

1. Didactic, which are used to expand horizons and cognitive activity, they form certain skills necessary for practical activities, in the course of their implementation, general educational skills and skills, as well as work skills, are developed. Didactic game is not just an integral component of active learning. Its meaning is wider.

2. Educators who bring up independence, will, cooperation, collectivism, sociability and communication, form certain approaches and positions, moral, aesthetic and worldview attitudes.

3. Developing, which develop the motivation of educational activities, attention, memory, speech, thinking, imagination, fantasy, creativity, empathy, reflection, the ability to compare, contrast, find analogies, optimal solutions. A.N. Leontiev believed that "the game is the freedom of the individual and imagination, the illusory realization of unrealizable interests."

4. Socializing, introducing to the norms and values of society, adapting to the conditions of a certain environment, teaching communication. By definition, L.S. Vygotsky: "The game is the space of the child's internal socialization, a means of assimilating social attitudes."

By type of activity, the games are divided into:

- physical (motor);
- intellectual (mental);
- labor;
- social;-psychological.

According to the nature of the gaming technique, the game can be divided into:

- subject;
- plot;
- role-playing;
- business;
- imitation;
- dramatization games.

The place and role of game technology in the educational process, the combination of game and learning elements largely depend on the teacher's understanding of the functions of pedagogical games. The systematic and purposeful use of game methods can give certain results, both in changing the basic personality traits and in the effectiveness of educational activities.

Primary school age is characterized by brightness and immediacy of perception, ease of entering into images. Children are easily involved in any activity, especially in a game, organize themselves in a group game, continue playing with objects, toys, non-imitation games appear. The concept of game methods and techniques in learning.

As mentioned above, the game as a method of learning, transferring the experience of older generations to younger people has been used since antiquity. In a modern school that relies on the activation and intensification of the educational process, gaming activities are used in

the following cases:

- as an independent method for mastering a certain topic;
- as elements, sometimes very essential, of some other method;
- as a whole lesson or part of it (introduction, explanation, consolidation, control or exercise);
- it is possible to use the game when organizing extra-curricular activities.

Games that can be used in literacy lessons:

"Bukvograd"

Equipment: each student has an envelope with several (from three to five) letter elements cut out of cardboard.

I propose to take out the letter elements from the envelope and fold them so that there are no extra elements left. The one who completes the task first wins.

"Red Blue"

Equipment: blue and red mugs for each player, forfeits.

I pronounce the vowel sound, the students repeat it, raising the red circle. When I say a consonant, the children raise the blue circle. For each mistake, children pay a fant. The winner is the one who has all the forfeits left.

The same game can be played to determine the softness, hardness of consonants. It will be called "Hard - Soft" and the equipment will include blue and green circles.

Games that can be played in the lessons of the world around:

"What changed?"

Equipment: subject pictures.

On the typesetting canvas, I expose subject pictures: flowers, leaves, fruits. On command, the children close their eyes, I change the location of the pictures or remove one or two pictures. Children must identify what has changed.

"What grows where?"

Equipment: wooden stick.

I give the stick to the children in turn and name the plant. Taking the stick, the student must quickly answer where it grows - in the garden, in the field, in the forest, in the pond and pass the stick to me.

Games that can be played in the Russian language lessons:

"One - many "

Equipment: ball.

I throw the ball to one of the children and name one object. The student who caught the ball must name a word denoting many such objects and throw the ball to me. Whoever gave the correct answer gets a token.

"Who is bigger?"

I divide the class into two teams. I call verbs in the indefinite form. Each team selects the same-root verbs with prefixes for these verbs. For example: walk - leave, come, move, etc. The team that picks up the largest number of single-root words wins.

CONCLUSION

The study of the theoretical foundations of gaming activity allows us to conclude that the game has a number of important functions, as well as a great educational potential. The game also has its own goals and objectives. The game method is a means of increasing the effectiveness of the lesson, since thanks to the game a favorable atmosphere appears in the

classroom, interest in learning is formed, the active participation of children during the lesson is generated, and discipline improves. Also, the game contributes to the emancipation of children in the classroom and affects their emotional state.

Consideration of the characteristics and functions of game activity showed that the game can be used as a teaching method in elementary school. At the initial stage of learning, games must be included in the educational process, since properly selected and organized games help to form a steady interest of students in this subject, activate the learning process, increase the concentration of students' attention, and facilitate the perception and assimilation of educational material.

References:

1. Anikeeva, N. P. Education with a game / N. P. Anikeeva - M.: Education, 1987. - 144 p.
2. Bogomolova, N. N. Situational role-playing game as an active method of socio-psychological training / N. N. Bogomolova // Theoretical and methodological problems of social psychology. - M.: Publishing House of Moscow. University. - 1977. - S. 192-193.
3. Vygotsky, L. S. The game and its role in the mental development of the child / L. S. Vygotsky // Questions of psychology. - No. 6. - S. 61-64.
4. Zhukovskaya, R. I. Game and its pedagogical significance. / R. I. Zhukovskaya. - M.: Pedagogy, 1975. - 112p.
5. Zanko, S. T. Game and teaching. / S. T. Zanko, Yu. S. Tyunikov, S. M. Tyunnikova. - M.: "Logos", 1992, part 1. - 125 p.
6. Game modeling in the activity of a teacher: Textbook for students of higher educational institutions / Ed. V. A. Slastenina, I. A. Kolesnikova. - M.: Academy, 2006. - 368 p.
7. Markova, A. K. Psychology of language acquisition as a means of communication / A. K. Markova. - M.: Pedagogy, 1974. - 240 p.
8. Mukhina, V. S. Child psychology / V. S. Mukhina. - M.: Enlightenment, 1985. - 250 p. S. 115.
9. Pidkasisty P.I., Khaidarov Zh.S. Game technology in learning and development: Textbook. M., 1996.
10. Sergeeva, I. S. Game technologies in the education of preschoolers and younger schoolchildren. Guidelines / I.S. Sergeeva, F.S. Gainullov. - M.: KnoRus, 2016. - 112 p.
11. Sergeeva, I.S. Game technologies in the education of preschoolers and younger schoolchildren. Methodological guide / I.S. Sergeyev. - M.: KnoRus, 2018. - 501 p.
12. Stepanova, E. L. Game as a means of developing interest in the language being studied / E. L. Stepanova // IYaSh. - 2004. - No. 2. - S. 66-68.
13. Filatov, V. M. Role-playing games in the classroom in a foreign language in primary school / V. M. Filatov // Klass, 1995. - No. 4 - P. 12-15.
14. Finogenov A.V. Game technologies at school: Textbook-method. allowance / A.V. Finogenov, V.E. Filippov. Krasnoyarsk: Krasnoyars. state un-t, 2001.
15. Khaidarov, Zh. S., Pidkasisty P. I. Game technology in learning and development / V. M. Filatov, P. I. Pidkasisty - M., 1996. - 272 p.
16. Shmakov S.A. Student games are a cultural phenomenon. M., 1994.
17. Elkonin, D. B. Psychology of the game / D. B. Elkonin. - M.: Enlightenment, 1987. - 350 s